

CUSP

RESEARCH ROADMAP

2026–2032

Informing and advising on the state of the art, gaps, and future needs in micro- and nanoplastic and health research in Europe.

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doi: [10.5281/zenodo.17467125](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17467125)

CUSP, the European Research Cluster on the health impacts of *micro- and nano-plastics* (MNPs), brings together five Horizon 2020 research projects to collaboratively explore the health impacts of MNP. By addressing cross-cutting themes, CUSP enhances synergies and maximises the impact of research outcomes.

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These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 964827 (AURORA), No. 965173 (IMPTOX), No. 965196 (PlasticHeal), No. 965367 (PlasticsFatE), and No. 964766 (POLYRISK).

CUSP RESEARCH ROADMAP

2026-2032

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) have been detected in air, food, water, and in human blood, lungs, and placenta. Emerging evidence shows that these particles can cause inflammation, oxidative stress, and immune disturbances in cell-based or whole animal tests. Yet, significant knowledge gaps remain that hinder the reliable risk assessment of MNPs for humans, particularly regarding the health effects of long-term, low-level exposure and the risks for vulnerable groups such as children, pregnant women, and workers.

The CUSP Research Roadmap 2026-2032 was developed by five Horizon 2020 projects (AURORA, IMPTOX, PlasticHeal, PlasticsFatE, POLYRISK) dedicated to researching the human health impacts of MNPs. It lays out the critical knowledge gaps and enabling of evidence-based action, focusing on five key areas:

MATERIALS AND METHODS

creating harmonized tools and reference materials to reliably measure MNPs.

HAZARD ASSESSMENT

investigating how particle size, shape, and chemical composition influence health effects.

EXPOSURE ASSESSMENT

understanding how people encounter MNPs in daily life, at work, and through food and water.

RISK ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORKS

integrating data on exposure and hazards to guide regulation and policy.

MITIGATION MEASURES

identifying strategies to reduce emissions, minimize exposure, and promote safer plastic use.

The CUSP Roadmap identifies 22 priority research needs, grouped by timeframe:

- **Immediate needs (2026–2028):** establishing reference materials, harmonizing methods, and developing sensitive models and biomarkers.
- **Mid-term needs (2027–2032):** scaling up human bio-monitoring, refining risk assessment tools, and improving real-world exposure studies.
- **Long-term needs (beyond 2032):** understanding chronic low-dose effects, complex mixtures, and environmentally aged particles to support comprehensive regulation.

The CUSP Roadmap is a blueprint for action. It sets clear priorities for research, policy, and outreach, and provides the evidence base needed to guide regulation and innovation. It identifies the need for policymakers, scientists, and industry to work together strategically to reduce risks, accelerate the transition toward safer and more sustainable alternatives, and ultimately protect public health from the harms caused by MNPs.

The urgency to address these risks has been reinforced by recent global developments. In August 2025, negotiations for a UN Plastics Treaty in Geneva stalled without agreement on managing plastic production across the full life cycle. At the same time, the Lancet Commission on Plastics and Health and the UN Environment Programme (UNEP) have warned that plastic pollution is a growing global health burden.

An important normative value of the European Union is the precautionary principle, which states that lack of scientific certainty should not stand in the way of preventing potential harm to human health. Given the existing and emerging evidence for the harms inflicted by plastics on human health across all life stages, it is important to prevent further adverse impacts by implementing evidence-based mitigation measures, even in the absence of abundant evidence of the harms of MNPs.

INTRODUCTION

Plastics have enabled global economic development. However, with increased plastics production and consumption, the negative side effects of this continuous growth are becoming increasingly apparent and require urgent, dedicated responses. Current plastic consumption patterns are unsustainable and are projected to double by 2050 (based on 2020 levels, 380.6 Mt) and increase threefold by 2100. [1] Due to the link between plastic production and pollution, plastic leakage to the environment under a business-as-usual scenario is anticipated to double, resulting in 121 million metric tonnes of mismanaged waste by 2050. [2] The European Commission's policies address many aspects of plastics pollution, such as micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs), with a goal to reduce their release into the environment by 30% by 2030. [3] Current unintentional releases of MNPs to the environment are estimated to range between 0.7 and 1.8 million tonnes (data from 2019).[4]

Plastics pose risks to human health across every stage of their life cycle, from fossil fuel extraction and production to use, disposal, and environmental degradation. During production, workers and communities near petrochemical facilities are exposed to air and water pollutants linked to respiratory diseases, cancers, and adverse reproductive outcomes. [5] In the use phase, plastic products can leach harmful chemicals such as bisphenols, phthalates, and flame retardants, which are associated with endocrine disruption, developmental toxicity, and metabolic disorders. [6] Use, disposal and environmental weathering release MNPs, which have been detected in human tissues, including the blood, placenta, brain, and lungs, with emerging evidence of inflammatory, oxidative, and immunological effects [7-11] and potential associated clinical disorders. Beyond direct health effects, plastics also harm human health indirectly e.g. through ecosystem disruption and the contribution of plastic production and incineration to greenhouse gas emissions, which in turn drive climate change and its associated health impacts. [4] This roadmap focuses on MNPs as a critical component of the plastic life cycle, where significant research gaps remain in understanding human exposure, associated health effects, and effective mitigation strategies.

Humans are exposed to MNPs through inhalation, contamination of drinking water and via the food chain. Additional known exposure routes include medical practices (intravenous infusions, dialysis, implants, etc.). It is also well established that humans are exposed to plastic chemicals e.g.: during the normal and intended use of plastic food contact materials, chemicals migrate into foods and are ingested. At least 1446 plastic food contact chemicals have been measured in humans, including 375 chemicals known to be of concern to human health. Plastic chemicals may also be

transferred dermally through skin contact (e.g., using personal care products). [12-13] MNPs are vectors for human exposure to plastic chemicals and also to absorbed persistent environmental pollutants (like DDT, dioxin, pesticides, etc.)

Reliable scientific data show that MNPs have been detected in air, water, soil, food, and even in human biological samples. [11] Previously, the sources of human exposure to MNPs had not been fully characterised, and their impacts on health were not sufficiently investigated to inform reliable regulatory risk assessment and management with the aim of effectively protecting public health. Therefore, in CUSP (the European Research Cluster to understand the impact of MNPs on human health), we performed focused scientific research on closing these pertinent knowledge gaps and have made significant progress since our work started in 2021. We have generated a better understanding of the presence, characteristics, and potential health effects of MNPs with regard to human health, and much of this new evidence has been captured in the three CUSP policy briefs [14]. Still, many data gaps remain that are essential for the reliable human health risk assessment of MNPs.

From 2021 to 2025, the five Horizon Europe projects within CUSP (AURORA, IMPTOX, PlasticsFatE, PlasticHeal, and POLYRISK) have investigated MNPs' effects on the respiratory and gastrointestinal systems, placenta and early-life health, immune system, and genomic integrity. To ensure harmonisation and comparability across studies, CUSP research has been structured around several transversal themes (see [Figure 3](#)).

These efforts have significantly advanced MNP detection methods, hazard identification of different MNPs in diverse contexts, and human exposure assessment. However, given the previously underappreciated but large complexity of MNP research (see [BOX I. Key Challenges in Micro- and Nanoplastic \(MNP\) Research](#)), critical knowledge gaps remain, and fully assessing the risks of MNPs to human health requires further coordinated research. In the absence of a full human health risk assessment, mitigation strategies become important to reduce human exposure to plastics, MNPs and plastic chemicals, because there is reason for concern based on plastic chemicals' impacts on health, and MNPs' impacts on ecosystems and on other non-human organisms (see CUSP's policy briefs #2, #3). [14]

This CUSP Research Roadmap provides a structured overview of current knowledge, research gaps, and targeted recommendations for a comprehensive regulatory risk assessment. By identifying priority areas and addressing key uncertainties, it aims to advance risk assessment and support evidence-based decision-making to safeguard human health.

BOX I. Key Challenges in Micro- and Nanoplastic (MNP) Research

MNPs can be composed of many polymer types, contain a range of additives, and may age or weather in environmental conditions, either in external (e.g., water, air) or internal (e.g. respiratory or gastrointestinal tract) environments. MNPs can absorb environmental pollutants and microbes or their compo-

nents. Physicochemical properties of MNPs include size, shape, density, and surface chemistry; these properties can undergo further changes through environmental degradation, thereby increasing the physicochemical complexity (see [Figure 1](#)). Notably, in the environment MNPs will not appear as a single type

DIFFERENT SHAPES OF MNPs

EXAMPLES OF DIFFERENT SOURCES OF MNPs

DIFFERENT TYPES OF PLASTIC CHEMICALS

Figure 1: Microplastics have several different shapes, originate from different sources and therefore have different compositions, and contain a multitude of different chemicals, including additives and non-intentionally added substances. Adapted from Zurub et al. (2023) <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2023.1330396> and GRID-Arendal (2020). Hansen et al. (2023) <https://www.grida.no/resources/14864>.

of MNP, but as complex mixtures of different types combined with other particulate and non-particulate pollutants. MNPs' complexity impacts exposure assessment and hazard identification, and with that also risk characterisation and assessment.

The following issues have been identified as key overall challenges in MNP research:

A Field in Development. As an emerging discipline, microplastics research lacks established reference materials and protocols, requiring scientists to build methodologies from scratch.

Health Hazards and Risks are Not Understood. Although CUSP has developed several interconnected risk assessment frameworks and collected substantial knowledge about the potential toxic effects of a limited set of MNPs, significant gaps remain. Exact exposure levels are still unclear, and toxicological and health data from real-world exposures are largely missing. As a result, a conclusive determination of health risks is not yet possible.

Diverse Particle Characteristics. With thousands of different plastic types and products on the market, MNPs in the environment vary widely in polymer and **chemical composition (including virgin/primary vs. recycled plastics), shape, size, and density**, and because plastics are not inert, their chemical properties change as they age.

Lack of Standardisation. Labs use a variety of methods to analyse the properties and presence of MNPs. Only a few methods have been evaluated in Inter-Laboratory Comparisons (ILCs) with a limited variety of materials, making results still difficult to compare. This also applies to cell culture methods to analyse the toxicity of MNPs.

Difficulty in Producing Research-Grade MNPs. In-house production of MNPs ensure uniformity, but struggles to replicate real-world MNPs, and MNPs tend to age within a short period after synthesis/in-house production. Commercially available MNPs are limited and often unsuitable for research needs as they do not reflect real-world exposure (i.e., lack of diversity, not reflecting ageing, irrelevant sizes (e.g., sufficiently small), etc.) and may carry unknown (uncontrolled) chemical additives and contaminants.

Contamination Risk. MNPs are ubiquitous, making it extremely challenging to ensure that samples are not accidentally polluted by airborne or surface-deposited particles during sampling, storage and/or analysis, requiring researchers to take unprecedented precautions in all aspects of MNP research.

State of the Science

Analytical Methods and Representative Materials

Work within the CUSP cluster included the development of test materials, as well as collection and detection methods. Several methods have been subjected to Inter-Laboratory Comparisons (ILCs) for method-harmonisation purposes, particularly for MNP detection methods and particle size characterisation. The work done within CUSP emphasises the need for well-characterised MNP test materials. Also, the dissemination of knowledge on specifications of MNPs (size, shape, polymer type, etc.) is important for acquiring reference material status, according to international guidelines (ISO, NIST, ASTM). [15] Our work also highlights the importance of harmonised protocols for common analytical detection methods and sample preparation methods.

Hazard Assessment

All CUSP projects used *in vitro* cell culture methods to determine potential toxicities induced by MNPs. They varied from single cell to multicellular to even more complex human stem cell-derived advanced cell culture systems. By using selected read-out parameters, effects could be linked to key events of various relevant adverse outcome pathways (AOPs).

The used methods allowed for analysing cellular uptake of MNPs, as well as assessing the effects of MNPs on cell functions. Various cell systems were used (such as epithelial cells of lungs or intestine, various freshly isolated human leukocytes or cell lines) to explore epithelial barrier transfer, and effects on different cell types were found. Various types of MNPs, such as polyethylene (PE), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polypropylene (PP), polystyrene (PS), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polylactide (PLA), as well as rubber particles have been tested. The majority of tested MNPs

were pristine; however, aged MNPs were also examined. MNP ageing was achieved by treatment with UV light (and other means) to simulate weathering. In addition, effects of MNP-associated contaminants (chemical additives, pollutants, and microbial components) have been tested.

Data generated in CUSP show that, depending on polymer type, size, shape, and surface chemistry, MNPs induce cellular effects, such as mitochondrial and oxidative stress, increased lysosomal activity, increased cytokine production, genotoxic effects, and decreased viability. Effects of pristine MNPs occur at relatively high concentrations (>50–100 µg/mL), whereas weathered or chemically modified particles (with modified surface chemistry or biofilm) appeared to have more diverse effects, and generally at lower concentrations. For instance, MNPs with reactive surface chemical groups or microbial biofilm elicit production of proinflammatory mediators. This is in contrast to some other MNPs that lack reactive surface chemistry. Instead, these types of MNPs (including primary PVC, PP, and PA MNPs), rather inhibit cellular viability by decreasing mitochondrial activity and membrane integrity (release of lactate dehydrogenase).

MNPs caused minimal acute effects on barrier integrity (of intestinal, or blood-brain barriers) but some MNPs appeared to decrease integrity of lung epithelial cells. Chronic exposure to weathered MNPs appeared to increase permeability of intestinal epithelial barriers, allowing allergen transfer.

Several of the CUSP projects evaluated *in vitro* dosimetry using predictive models; however, these models are often unsuitable for testing because most MNPs assessed were heterogeneous, exhibiting broad variations in size and shape.

IMPTOX, PlasticsFatE, and PlasticHeal also used animal studies to investigate effects of MNPs. In invertebrate

models, most MNPs tested have been found to induce oxidative stress, inflammation, and DNA damages after chronic ingestion. Reproductive toxicity was also reported in these invertebrate models after chronic ingestion of test MNPs. In mammalian models, MNPs caused acute reaction of the gastrointestinal tract after acute (single-dose) exposure via ingestion, with apparent recovery over time for most endpoints apart from late-onset inflammation and DNA damage in the case of PS beads. When the same model was exposed repeatedly for a week to test MNPs via ingestion, more widespread effects on the gastrointestinal tract and secondary organs were identified, in a dose- and time-dependent

manner. Effects on the microbiome of these test organisms (*Drosophila* flies and mice) after exposure to MNPs via ingestion were also revealed; these effects were polymer-type dependent. Effects on the mouse respiratory tract after acute exposure were time, size, and polymer-type dependent, with test MNPs causing less lung reactions than the commercial PS beads. Repeating the exposure to test MNPs (daily for a week) did not increase the response, regardless of the dose used. No persistent adverse effects were observed following either acute or repeated respiratory exposure to the test MNPs.

Comparisons of *in vitro* findings and *in vivo* animal studies to human ob-

BOX II. What are the RIGHT MNPs?

Standard reference MNPs are needed for chemical analysis, toxicological assessments, and human health risk assessments. Commercially many types of MNPs are available [16] but many of these MNPs are not within the size range (<1µm) needed for MNP research. Specifically, standard reference MNPs are important for the following reasons:

- I. Physical and chemical properties of MNPs are relevant for assessing and evaluating their impacts on health:
 - a. Size, shape, polymer type, chemical composition, surface chemistry may all be relevant for the final outcome in test systems.
- II. Plastics are not inert: they will change their physical and chemical properties over time (also under standard lab-conditions) which makes working with MNPs very challenging. Careful precautions need to be taken to ensure longevity of produced MNPs for intra- and interlaboratory comparisons.
- III. Different types of standard reference MNPs are needed for:
 - a. Chemical analysis to determine EXPOSURE: harmonisation and calibration of measurement procedures.
 - b. Toxicological assessments to determine HAZARD: measurements of *in vitro* or *in vivo* effects of weathered MNPs would benefit from comparisons with physico-chemically standardised reference MNPs. With such comparisons, MNPs' structural alerts for hazard can be defined.
- IV. Exposure and hazard data with standard reference MNPs are needed for risk assessments and to train *in silico* prediction models.

servational studies are important for determining potential human health risks. The CUSP cluster performed a few human exposure scenario studies, including exposure to MNPs from urban traffic, indoor soccer playing fields, and in occupational settings. Findings indicate that exposure to MNPs induced short-term increases in blood leukocytes, as is also the case for other particulates. Currently, information is lacking to make further and more thorough comparisons. The only large-scale epidemiological study investigating MNP exposure during pregnancy is still ongoing in AURORA. More broadly, there is a global shortage of high-quality epidemiological research on MNPs and human health.

While outcomes from the five CUSP projects generally align well, several issues still require further attention. For instance, *in vitro* and *in vivo* test concentrations, testing methods and models, and time points and endpoints need harmonisation across different laboratories to provide data that can indeed be translated to real-world situations.

Exposure Assessment

CUSP projects have documented the presence of MNPs across multiple media, including air, water, food, and personal care products. MNPs have also been detected in human biological matrices such as blood and placenta samples from diverse populations. However, due to variability in analytical methods and the inherent complexity of MNPs' detection and characterisation, the results of these studies are not yet readily comparable or integratable. To support harmonisation across studies, an innovative, expert-driven mind map tool was developed to advance MNPs' exposure assessment. This structured framework organises over 250 interlinked terms and identifies five critical domains – MNPs' definition, purpose of assessment, exposure

scenarios, data collection and analysis, and methodological harmonisation – each addressing a key aspect of the complex process of assessing human exposure via ingestion, inhalation, and dermal contact (see [Figure 4](#)). The tool is intended for researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders engaged in MNP health risk assessment, enabling greater consistency, transparency, and comparability across the field.

Risk Assessment Frameworks

All CUSP projects have developed specific risk assessment frameworks (RAFTs) for assessing health risks of MNPs. The different RAFTs integrate MNP characteristics, exposure, hazard and/or risk factors to identify health risks. Currently, there is insufficient information to support a comprehensive risk assessment for any of the many types of MNPs – let alone for environmentally relevant complex mixtures. Even for PS, the most extensively studied polymer at the micro- and nanoscale, our understanding remains limited regarding how, and to what extent, observed effects vary with particle size and shape. All CUSP projects have identified critical data gaps and proposed targeted research to strengthen the frameworks needed for regulatory action.

The five RAFTs developed in CUSP each have a particular focus that matches the specific project objectives.

AURORA's RAFT focuses on health risks of MNPs on early-life health (i.e., developmental and reproductive toxicity) and emphasises MNPs' properties, dose-response data, exposure pathways, and proposes a tiered scoring system for risk management.

The **IMPTOX** RAFT aims to analyse allergies and asthma as health outcomes related to MNPs. It considers biological, chemical, and environmental hazards that determine how MNPs may

enhance the risk of allergic responses.

The RAFT of **PLASTICSFATE** evaluates the human health risks of MNPs using specific indicators, i.e., polymer type, product category, and additives. It aims to estimate exposure and hazard levels using data on release, degradation, environmental fate, and toxicity of MNPs.

PlasticRiskCat, developed by **PLASTICHEAL**, supports first-tier hazard assessment of pristine, commercial, and unintentionally produced MNPs. It uses radar plots to communicate hazards like carcinogenicity, mutagenicity, reproductive toxicity, and cardiovascular effects, with evidence strength ranging from “Very strong” to “Very weak.”

POLYRISK's RAFT focuses on inhalation exposure, and combines Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATAs) in a modular and adaptable way (e.g., to types of MNPs or to oral route of exposure), to link exposure to existing guidelines and tiered testing approaches for immunotoxicity.

The different RAFTs are complementary as AURORA and IMPTOX' RAFT are effect/endpoint-oriented, PlasticFatE's RAFT is product-oriented (input), Plasticheal's PlasticRiskCat tool provides an overview of existing hazard data, and POLYRISK's RAFT uses an exposure-route-specific way to assess health risks. While these five RAFTs are useful for their specific applicability domains, the next challenge is to align and combine the five frameworks into an overarching, more generally applicable framework. The work undertaken within CUSP has laid important groundwork for this development. Moving forward, integration of risk assessment frameworks from other national and international initiatives will also be essential to building a comprehensive and coherent risk assessment approach.

Summary of Findings

Risk assessment frameworks integrate hazard and exposure data but face challenges due to incomplete datasets. Standardisation of measurement methods and data reporting, updates to national and international policies, and effective health interventions are crucial for addressing potential health risks related to MNP exposures.

Figure 2 illustrates the four elements of risk assessment and highlights information requirements, as well as methods that are used to generate information. Knowledge gaps hinder complete risk assessment.

Figure 2: The figure illustrates the four steps of risk assessment: 1. Hazard identification, 2. Hazard characterisation, 3. Exposure assessment, 4. Risk characterisation. Different methods are applied for achieving each of these steps, based on the different information requirements. Key knowledge gaps are highlighted for hazard identification, hazard characterisation, and exposure assessment. Reliable risk characterisation is only possible if sufficient and reliable data exist for these first 3 steps of risk assessment.

Overview of the Research Roadmap

This roadmap combines the results of the 5 CUSP projects and highlights 5 key transversal themes (see [Figure 3](#)).

Findings from these five transversal themes are detailed in this research roadmap and complemented by an overview of key knowledge gaps and prioritised future research needs.

Figure 3: The five CUSP projects all addressed the five transversal themes described in the roadmap, but each project led a different group/theme, as illustrated by the thicker lines.

RESEARCH NEEDS

Overview of the research needs that have been identified for the 5 transversal themes in CUSP (status quo September 2025). The needs are developed and detailed in the following CUSP Roadmap sections. Research needs are intended to inform researchers and research funders, as well as other stakeholders.

Immediate Needs: 2026-2027; **Mid-Term Needs:** 2027-2032; **Long-Term Needs:** >2032.

Analytical Methods and Representative Materials

Immediate Needs (0–2 years)	Mid-Term Needs (2–5 years)	Long-Term Needs (>5 years)
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Focus on quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC)• Develop reporting standards for analytical methods• Develop relevant test & reference materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Improve sensitivity, reduce limits of detection• Harmonise analytical methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Speed up assessments (indicator polymers, tracers, bulk measurements)

Hazard Assessment

Immediate Needs (0–2 years)	Mid-Term Needs (2–5 years)	Long-Term Needs (>5 years)
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Develop quantitative <i>in vitro</i> test systems• Develop novel approaches for sensitive MNP detection <i>in situ</i>• Develop <i>in silico</i> kinetic models and quantitative <i>in vitro</i> to <i>in vivo</i> extrapolations• Develop reporting standards for hazard data	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Develop relevant, tiered approach for high-throughput testing	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Characterise hazards of real-life mnps• Identify the biological mechanisms of action of MNPs

Exposure Assessment

Immediate Need (0–2 years)	Mid-Term Needs (2–5 years)	Long-Term Needs (>5 years)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop reporting standards for studies assessing MNP exposure • Develop robust standard operating procedures (SOPs) and ILCs for mnp analysis in real-world samples • Develop interoperable data infrastructure and sharing platforms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investigate mnp polymer types and concentrations in tissues • Describe and control for real-world sample contamination • Develop human MNP biomonitoring at scale 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scale-up human biomonitoring studies and develop MNP exposure prediction

Risk Assessment Frameworks

Immediate Need (0–2 years)	Mid-Term Needs (2–5 years)	Long-Term Needs (>5 years)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop aggregated exposure assessment • Perform qualitative risk assessments of MNPs and mixtures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand exposure and effects in human populations • Generate hazard data for key plastic types • Generate hazard data for key plastic mixtures • Understand human health risks through epidemiological research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop quantitative risk assessments of MNPs and mixtures • Address social determinants and health inequities in MNP exposure and risk • Assess and amend existing test guidelines and frameworks

Mitigation Measures

Immediate Need (0–2 years)	Mid-Term Needs (2–5 years)	Long-Term Needs (>5 years)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify ongoing policy activities that can address MNP exposure mitigation • Identify which uses of plastics are essential • Promote public awareness and behaviour change to reduce MNP exposure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify criteria for developing low-migrating materials that are safe and sustainable by design • Develop an alternative materials substitution framework • Assess mitigation strategies and the risks of substitutes • Apply life cycle approaches to identify upstream MNP sources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate economic impacts and cost-effectiveness of policy measures

Table 1. CUSP Roadmap Research Needs. Overview by Thematic Research Areas and Immediate Needs (0–2 years), Mid-Term Needs (2–5 years) and Long-Term Needs (>5 years).

THEMATIC RESEARCH AREAS

Five transversal thematic research areas are key to filling knowledge gaps required for the reliable risk assessment of MNPS, for protecting human health, and for identifying evidence-based mitigation strategies to reduce the health impacts of MNPs. These areas are

1. [Analytical Methods and Representative Materials](#)
2. [Hazard Assessment](#)
3. [Exposure Assessment](#)
4. [Risk Assessment Frameworks](#)
5. [Mitigation Measures](#)

In this section, we explore each of these thematic areas, discuss the summary of findings from the CUSP cluster, highlight knowledge gaps and challenges based on the entire body of MNP research, and present research needs that have been prioritised according to their achievability and urgency (i.e., because they are needed for making progress on other priority research needs).

Analytical Methods and Representative Materials

Measuring MNPs in diverse (biological) samples is a prerequisite for hazard and exposure assessment, and this data is essential for human health risk assessments. To generate the necessary data, methods must be reliable and reproducible across different labs, allowing for comparisons of results. To achieve this, it is imperative to have reliable MNP reference standards that can be used across different labs to develop analytical methods and to calibrate analytical equipment. The development of such test materials, as well as developing the analytical methods, have been a key focus of the work in CUSP.

Summary of Findings

Test Materials

Several irregular shaped PE, PP, PA, PET, PLA, and PVC MNP test materials have been used within the CUSP cluster. Some are available as aged and labelled MNPs, enabling the study of their cell fate and biodistribution. However, most MNPs used are still in the experimental phase and not widely available.

Analytical Methods: Interlaboratory Comparisons (ILCs)

ILCs for particle size characterisation showed a high consistency between laboratories, using different methods, such as Laser Diffraction (LD) and Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS). CUSP addressed particles in the size range of small microplastics (1–200 μm) for laser diffraction and 50–400 nm for the DLS. It was shown that sample preparation and especially dispersion is crucial to achieving consistent results. [14]

The ILC by CUSP for well-accepted microplastics detection methods, including Micro-Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (μ -FTIR), Micro-Raman Spectroscopy (μ -Raman), Laser Direct Infrared Imaging Spectroscopy (LDIR), Pyrolysis–Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry (Py-GC/MS), and Thermal Extraction and Desorption Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry (TED-GC/MS), revealed the challenges in quantitative measurements. While the polymers could be identified in all laboratories, quantification (both of particle numbers as well as of total MNP mass) was more challenging. Quantification worked quite well within the tolerance level using mass-based methods at relatively high concentrations. Number-based methods were much more challenging. Lab-to-lab variation was high due to limitations of the instruments, use

of technical equipment and analytical software from different manufacturers, as well as different equipment settings, including quality threshold.

Knowledge Gaps and Challenges

- 1. Limited availability of well-characterised reference MNPs:** There is a scarcity of reference materials with clearly defined properties, including particles in the nano size range and realistic, environmentally aged samples that mimic real-world plastic pollution. An important issue is that MNPs also age under lab conditions, unless preservatives are added.
- 2. Lack of standardisation in physicochemical analytical methods:** Many analytical techniques that have been used to assess various types of MNPs are not standardised across laboratories, leading to inconsistencies in ILCs.
- 3. Missing ILCs:** While some ILCs have been carried out in CUSP, not all newly developed sample preparation methods have been assessed in ILCs. Therefore, there is a need to carry out additional ILCs using emerging analytical tools and novel sample preparation methods.
- 4. Insufficient understanding of environmental ageing and weather effects:** The impact of environmental ageing and weathering on MNPs is not well understood, hindering accurate risk assessments.
- 5. Inadequate comprehensive analysis of test/reference materials:** Existing test/reference materials have not been thoroughly analysed using multiple physicochemical methods, which is essential to prevent misinterpretation in exposure, risk, or hazard studies.

Research Needs

Immediate Needs (0–2 years / 2026–2028)

FOCUS ON QUALITY ASSURANCE AND QUALITY CONTROL (QA/QC)

There is a need to increase awareness within the scientific community regarding best practices for handling and assessing test and reference MNPs under diverse experimental conditions in order to ensure the generation of robust, reliable, and reproducible study results.

DEVELOP REPORTING STANDARDS FOR ANALYTICAL METHODS

To advance the field of MNP exposure research, standardised reporting guidelines for analytical methods must be developed. Such standards should ensure that sufficient methodological detail is provided to allow for critical evaluation of analytical quality and reproducibility. Moreover, establishing minimal reporting criteria will facilitate the integration and comparison of results across studies by making the analytical conditions and limitations under which data were generated more transparent and interpretable.

DEVELOP RELEVANT TEST & REFERENCE MATERIALS

A more systematic and comprehensive set of test and reference materials is urgently needed, incorporating a wide range of particle types with well-defined and fully characterised physicochemical properties. Such materials are essential to ensure reproducibility, enable method validation, and support the comparability of results across studies.

Mid-Term Needs (2–5 years / 2027–2032)

IMPROVE SENSITIVITY, REDUCE LIMITS OF DETECTION

Attention should also be directed toward the development and implementation of emerging technologies with enhanced sensitivity and lower detection limits to improve the accuracy, reliability, and resolution of MNP detection and analysis.

HARMONISE ANALYTICAL METHODS

Harmonisation studies should be conducted using well-established analytical techniques, incorporating all necessary quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) measures to ensure accurate, reliable, and comparable detection of MNPs across laboratories and studies.

Long-Term Needs (>5 years / beyond 2032)

SPEED UP ASSESSMENTS (INDICATOR POLYMERS, TRACERS, BULK MEASUREMENTS)

Given the anticipated volume of required analyses, there is a pressing need for medium- to high-throughput analytical methods to assess the occurrence of MNPs. This necessitates the development or improvement of technologies capable of delivering rapid, sensitive, and reliable measurements, enabling large-scale monitoring and risk assessment efforts.

Hazard Assessment

Characterising and describing the hazards of MNPs to human health is essential for carrying out human health risk assessments. Hazard assessments for MNPs utilise methods that range from *in vitro* (cell-based test systems) to *in vivo* (whole organism testing), as well as studies in humans. A prerequisite for carrying out experiments to characterise hazards is the availability of well-characterised test and reference MNPs, as well as those which are relevant for human exposures (weathered or aged MNPs, with relevant size ranges).

Summary of Findings

CUSP has documented the carcinogenicity, mutagenicity, and reproductive (CMR) toxicity, as well as immunotoxicity, of MNPs, revealing their ability to induce oxidative stress, inflammation, genotoxicity, and adverse outcomes such as allergies and fibrosis. Smaller particles show stronger mutagenic effects, and co-exposure with pollutants can modify these impacts. Results show that MNPs can cross the placental barrier, accumulating in fetal organs and causing biological effects in liver and lipid metabolism, raising concerns for pregnancy and early development.

CUSP has also observed effects of MNPs on lung and immune cells, with cellular uptake, oxidative stress, and mitochondrial dysfunction observed in several cellular models. Toxicity appears to be influenced by factors like size, shape, surface charge, and persistence. Studies by CUSP have shown MNPs' ability to alter macrophage function and dendritic cell maturation, affecting adaptive immune responses that can be linked to the induction of allergies.

In the digestive system, MNPs affect intestinal bacteria and disrupt intestinal homeostasis, with exposure linked to changes in microbial composition. Additionally, MNP digestion alters the particle properties and affects protein digestion, altering peptide bioavailability and potentially influencing the development of food allergies.

CUSP research has yielded important insights into the biological effects of MNPs through a range of *in vitro* models. MNPs such as PS, PET, PE, PP, PVC, and PA have demonstrated cellular toxicity at concentrations (>50–100 µg/mL), with some effects also observed at lower concentrations (as low as 10 µg/mL). Toxicological outcomes are influenced by key particle characteristics, including size, shape, and chemical composition. CUSP data further indicate that oxidised

surface groups or contamination with microbial components can enhance the proinflammatory potential of MNPs.

In addition, *in vitro* models mimicking lung, placental, and gastrointestinal systems have shown that some MNPs increase epithelial permeability and trigger inflammatory, allergic, and immune responses – particularly when co-exposed with pathogens or allergens. These findings emphasise the importance of both physicochemical properties and environmental context in determining the biological activity and potential health risks of MNPs.

Knowledge Gaps and Challenges

- 1. MNPs behave differently in culture media depending on their physicochemical properties:** For instance, depending on MNPs' densities, they may float or sink and sediment to layer on top of plated cells. In addition, they may clump together, and hence not be uniformly distributed in solutions. These particle properties complicate concentration-effect comparisons between different MNPs. CUSP partners have used the Distorted Grid (DG) model for dosimetry predictions in *in vitro* studies, but the model needs to be further validated with additional MNPs. MNPs behave differently in culture media depending on their physicochemical properties.
- 2. MNPs' physicochemical properties are key to toxicity:** CUSP has shown that physicochemical properties of MNPs (i.e., reactive surface, shape) determine the toxicological effect of MNPs. The relationship between physicochemical properties of MNPs and potential toxicities is still far from understood.
- 3. Real-world MNPs are different:** CUSP found stronger and different effects of environmentally weathered or aged MNPs. However, physicochemical effects of weathering or ageing on MNPs are not well known. In addition, we lack understanding of the combined effects of microplastics with other environmental factors, such as adsorbed chemicals, microbial contamination, or allergens.
- 4. Assessing hazards from *in silico* to *in vitro* and *in vivo*:** Tiered testing approaches that help to predict hazards of MNPs are part of CUSP's achievements but need to be harmonised and validated.

Research Needs

Immediate Needs (0–2 years / 2026–2028)

DEVELOP QUANTITATIVE *IN VITRO* TEST SYSTEMS

Laboratory-based experimental setups are essential to precisely and quantitatively assess toxicological responses and to determine the minimal dose required to trigger an effect. The *in vitro* approaches developed should be of human relevance, with particular emphasis on capturing non-standard endpoints. Alternatively, high-throughput *in vitro* methods should be explored to enable rapid screening of MNP effects. To improve exposure assessment and testing, advanced models for *in vitro* dosimetry – such as the Distorted Grid (DG) model piloted in CUSP – require further validation using realistic MNPs.

DEVELOP NOVEL APPROACHES FOR SENSITIVE MNP DETECTION *IN SITU*

Enhanced detection and characterisation of MNPs (e.g., fluorescently or metal-labelled MNPs) in cell culture systems is needed to assess MNP concentrations crossing epithelial layers or reaching the cytosol. This will allow for the description of effective doses (e.g., internal vs. external), short- and long-term intracellular fate, and bioaccumulation, and is especially needed for nano-sized plastic particles.

DEVELOP *IN SILICO* KINETIC MODELS AND QUANTITATIVE *IN VITRO* TO *IN VIVO* EXTRAPOLATIONS

Empirical studies have detected MNPs in various human organs. However, due to their wide variability in composition and characteristics, it is nearly impossible to empirically map external to internal exposure. To address this, *in silico* particle physiologically based kinetic (PBK) models have been developed to simulate uptake, distribution, metabolism, and excretion of MNPs.

While PBK models are well-established for chemicals, their application to particles is still emerging. Existing particle PBK models provide initial insights but also highlight key data gaps – such as uptake rates across organs (lungs, gut, placenta, blood-brain barrier), tissue accumulation, and excretion.

REPORTING STANDARDS

Strengthening hazard assessment of MNPs requires standardised reporting and harmonised documentation. Key elements include consistently reported metadata on MNP properties. Essential elements to report include detailed physicochemical characteristics of the test MNPs (e.g., size distribution, shape, polymer type, % of recycled materials, surface chemistry, degree of weathering or oxidation, and presence of chemical additives or adsorbed contaminants), as well as relevant information on cell types, culture conditions, exposure concentrations, time points, and endpoints assessed. Using structured templates, SOPs, and minimal

information checklists – like MIAME, used for microarrays – can improve transparency and reproducibility. This approach supports high-quality studies and enables data integration into existing datasets, modelling, and regulatory use.

Mid-Term Needs (2–5 years / 2027–2032)

DEVELOP RELEVANT, TIERED APPROACH FOR HIGH-THROUGHPUT TESTING

In the coming 2–5 years, the tiered testing system established within CUSP will need to be further extended and validated. A key priority is the development and refinement of fit-for-purpose test methods that enable meaningful translation from *in vitro* findings to *in vivo* outcomes. Ideally, first-tier assays should support higher-throughput screening to evaluate a broad range of MNPs, including both pristine and environmentally-weathered forms. Furthermore, there is a critical need for studies that compare the biological effects of chronic long-term, low-dose exposures with those of acute, high-dose exposures, to better reflect real-world exposure scenarios and improve risk characterisation.

Long-Term Needs (>5 years / beyond 2032)

CHARACTERISE HAZARDS OF REAL-LIFE MNPs

Understanding the potential hazards of MNPs that closely resemble those present in the environment is essential for relevant risk assessment. Critical physicochemical properties – such as surface chemistry, size, shape, and degree of weathering – must be systematically linked to observed biological effects. To achieve this, future research should include comprehensive studies on aged or environmentally-weathered MNPs, which may exhibit altered surface reactivity, contaminant load, and biological interactions compared to pristine particles. Establishing such property-effect relationships will be pivotal in identifying the most hazardous particle types and informing both hazard prioritization and regulatory decision-making.

IDENTIFY THE BIOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF ACTION OF MNPs

Identifying how MNPs interact with biological systems is crucial, as it supports the determination of potential toxicity, bioaccumulation, and long-term health effects. Further, it provides the scientific basis for evidence-based regulations and safety guidelines, informs pollution mitigation measures, and supports the development of new approach methodologies (NAMs) that reduce the need for *in vivo* testing while improving hazard characterisation. Knowledge of MNPs' interactions at the molecular level can guide the development of alternative materials leading to less harmful MNPs.

Exposure Assessment

Like hazard assessment, characterising and describing human exposure to MNPs is essential for carrying out human health risk assessments. Exposure assessments are based on measurements of MNPs in air, drinking water, and food, in addition to estimates or empirical data of MNPs in humans, such as levels in blood, faeces, urine, and other fluids, or in specific tissues and organs. Prerequisites for reliable exposure assessments are analytical detection methods and the knowledge of real-world human exposures to MNPs.

Summary of Findings

CUSP has collected sampling procedures and exposure/biomarker protocols used by the CUSP projects in their different environmental and human (bio)monitoring studies. [17] This is an attempt to start the harmonisation that has been identified as essential. This collection, when finalised, can be used as a reference or point-of-departure for future MNP human studies.

The process of MNP exposure assessment was outlined by drawing a mind map of all measurements and corner stones that may provide guidance to perform exposure assessment (see [Figure 4](#)).

Physicochemical assessment of characteristics (type of polymer, size, shape, and surface chemistry) and amount (both total mass and particle count) have been performed in human samples (exhaled breath condensate, blood, urine) from various scenario studies (internal exposure) and in environmental and food samples (external exposure). Based on the current understanding of MNP hazards from *in vitro* findings, a comprehensive characterisation and quantification of MNP in human samples is considered fundamentally important for reliable human risk assessments.

As part of its efforts to consolidate the current evidence base, CUSP has conducted a systematic review of contemporary scientific literature (from 2019 onward) reporting MNPs exposure in human biological samples. While numerous studies have documented the presence of MNPs in matrices such as blood, placenta, or faeces, most investigations are limited by small sample sizes (typically fewer than 50 individuals) and insufficient QA/QC procedures. Common limitations include potential contamination during sampling and analysis, and inconsistent reporting of methodological details. As a result, robust quantitative

data on population-level MNP exposure remains scarce. Furthermore, the predominance of studies conducted in clinical or hospital settings limits the generalisability of findings to broader population exposures.

In CUSP, MNPs were detected in household dust samples using pyrolysis-gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (Py-GC-MS). The analysis revealed significant variation in MNP concentrations between households. However, the specific sources and determinants contributing to these differences remain poorly understood. This finding highlights the need for further investigation into indoor MNP sources and exposure pathways to better assess residential exposure risks and inform mitigation measures.

Assessment of tyre wear rubber particles (TWRP) in air samples as an example of aged/weathered MNPs that humans are exposed to has proven very difficult and time consuming. A new methodology for air sampling has been developed and used in a traffic-related scenario study. [18] Exposure levels detected in the air appeared to be related to the amount of traffic in the vicinity of sampling. Increased levels of leukocytes were detected in blood samples shortly after exposure to traffic-related MNPs and could be partly attributed to rubber MNPs.

Inhalable MNPs, measured in ambient air within occupational settings (i.e., factories) using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), were the highest reported so far among studies using similar analytical methods. More than 11 polymers were detected, and most particles were less than 50 µm in size.

CUSP data confirms that real-life scenario studies need to account for the complexity of sampling circumstances. CUSP has used adequate QA/QC measures as these are essential to prevent contamination with MNPs due to handling sampling devices and materials (e.g., filters, tubes, syringes, storage containers, etc.).

Knowledge Gaps and Challenges

1. **Exposure-relevant properties of real-world MNPs are complex:** Knowledge on MNPs' chemical additives and other surface-associated chemicals or contaminants (heavy metals, persistent organic pollutants, biocorona including microorganisms, etc.) is limited, although these aspects can affect internal exposure assessment.

Figure 4. Essential components of MNP exposure assessment

2. **Human exposures to and fate of MNP in human tissues is largely unknown:** Data on human MNP exposures (external and internal) and their determinants as well as pharmacokinetic models are largely lacking due to limited high-quality studies.
3. **Exposure sources assessment is not yet fit-for-purpose:** Analytical techniques to determine MNPs in real-world samples (air, food, blood, etc.) need further improvement and validation (e.g. robust sample collection and processing).
4. **Population data are missing:** Reliable, and scalable biomonitoring techniques are currently lacking, and this is hampering large studies on MNP exposure and human health effects.

Research Needs

Immediate Needs (0–2 years / 2026–2028)

DEVELOP REPORTING STANDARDS FOR STUDIES ASSESSING MNP EXPOSURE

Consensus process to reach agreement on essential reporting aspects, such as sample processing procedures, methods and key technical parameters for MNP measurement, and QA/QC considerations, will enable comparison, synthesis, and possible extrapolation of findings across studies (e.g., meta-analysis).

DEVELOP ROBUST SOPs AND ILCs FOR MNP ANALYSIS IN REAL-WORLD SAMPLES

To advance the reliability and comparability of MNP data across environmental and biological studies, it is essential to develop and implement robust SOPs and ILCs for the analysis of real-world samples. This includes improving understanding of contamination risks during sampling and storage, identifying low-contamination materials and products, and determining optimal storage conditions to minimise particle degradation and ageing. Parallel efforts must focus on characterising the complex and heterogeneous properties of real-life MNPs, which differ significantly from pristine reference and test materials. These properties – such as irregular shapes and sizes, surface oxidation, adsorbed contaminants, and aggregation behaviour – can influence analytical detection, biological reactivity, and environmental fate. Integrating this knowledge into SOPs will help ensure that methods are fit for purpose, reflect realistic exposure scenarios, and support the development of harmonised, high-quality datasets suitable for risk assessment and regulatory use.

DEVELOP INTEROPERABLE DATA INFRASTRUCTURE AND SHARING PLATFORMS

To support harmonisation and cross-study comparability, create interoperable databases and informatics tools for micro- and nanoplastic data. This includes harmonised vocabularies, metadata standards, and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles to support meta-analysis and model validation.

Mid-Term Needs (2–5 years / 2027–2032)

INVESTIGATE MNP POLYMER TYPES AND CONCENTRATIONS IN TISSUES

Increase understanding of the amounts of MNPs that can cross biological barriers – including those in the intestinal and respiratory tracts, as well as the placenta and blood-brain barrier – and identify the physicochemical and biological factors that influence their uptake. This knowledge is critical to improving the accuracy, relevance, and realism of human exposure assessments.

DESCRIBE AND CONTROL FOR REAL-WORLD SAMPLE CONTAMINATION

In addition to harmonising protocols and ILCs, method development should prioritise standardisation under realistic, non-laboratory conditions. This includes accounting for variability introduced by real-world sample matrices, storage conditions, and common contamination sources (e.g., airborne fibres, plastic equipment). Consumer behaviours and lifestyle differences, such as indoor activities, product use, or ventilation patterns, can influence both exposure levels and sampling contamination risk. Therefore, SOPs and ILCs should be validated not only in controlled lab settings but also in the environments and conditions in which they will be applied. Doing so will increase the robustness, applicability, and comparability of MNP data across research contexts and population studies.

DEVELOP HUMAN MNP BIOMONITORING AT SCALE

Direct quantification of MNPs can be labour intensive and time/money consuming. The field needs to develop easy to measure exposure biomarkers that are predictive of internal MNP levels (e.g., using metabolic signatures can be a cost-effective way to estimate human MNP exposure in diverse populations).

Long-Term Needs (>5 years / beyond 2032)

SCALE-UP HUMAN BIOMONITORING STUDIES AND DEVELOP MNP EXPOSURE PREDICTION

To strengthen the evidence base for human health risk assessment, large-scale, population-based studies on MNP exposure are urgently needed. These studies should use sufficiently powered sample sizes to detect meaningful associa-

tions and reflect diverse populations in terms of geography, socioeconomic status, occupation, age, and life stage. Special emphasis should be placed on including vulnerable and underrepresented groups who may face higher exposure levels or increased susceptibility to health effects. Biological samples from a range of matrices should be collected using standardised protocols and rigorous QA/QC procedures. In parallel, efforts should focus on developing and validating exposure

prediction models that integrate environmental monitoring data, lifestyle information, and biomarker profiles to support cost-effective exposure estimation in human biomonitoring. Importantly, these efforts must be linked to biological readouts and health phenotypes to enable robust interpretation of exposure-health relationships and increase the utility of data for risk assessment and public health action.

Risk Assessment Frameworks

All five CUSP projects have made substantial progress in developing risk assessment frameworks (RAFTs) tailored to different aspects of MNPs and human health. The CUSP RAFTs, while complementary in their focus, highlight the need for alignment and integration into a unified, more generalisable framework. This work establishes a strong foundation for future collaboration across European and global initiatives aimed at advancing MNP risk assessment and informing regulatory action.

Summary of Findings

CUSP projects have generated RAFTs that address the specific aims of each project.

AURORA has focused its RAFT on assessing the risks of MNP on early-life health. This framework has been published in *Microplastics and Nanoplastics*. [19] The framework has been adapted from established chemical RAFTs (e.g., WHO, IAAC) and aims to address key risk assessment (RA) components, identify information to inform each stage, and highlight data gaps that hinder RA progression. The AURORA RAFT details the potential pathways through which early-life populations may be exposed to MNPs, including maternal, placental, and fetal routes, highlighting the importance of understanding the characteristics and quantities of MNPs reaching these vulnerable populations and the need for improved analytical techniques to assess exposure. The framework recommends a weight of evidence (WoE) approach, relying on qualitative assessments when quantitative data are lacking. It also suggests developing a semi-quantitative tiered scoring system to categorise MNPs based on their risk potential, facilitating targeted research and regulatory actions.

PlasticsFatE has developed a “prospective multi-criteria decision system” (PMCDs) as a tool to assist the design phase of material and product development. Based on a limited amount of input data, this online tool aims to estimate the

risks to humans of using plastics for specific applications. In this way, different physicochemical properties can be compared. The result is intended to provide guidance on the selection of a polymer for a particular type of application or product that poses the lowest possible risk to humans. The PMCDs enables a risk banding evaluation for the potential impact of MNPs on human health. Input information is required from the user, which is usually available in the initial stages of material selection. Based on the information entered, the PMCDs estimates the potential exposure and hazard of MNPs to humans. The predicted risk level is expressed graphically by linking exposure and hazard. The assessment of the exposure potential of MNPs considers their release, degradation of macroplastics, fate in environmental compartments, and occurrence in food and drink.

PlasticHeal has proposed an RA approach termed PlasticRiskCat to support researchers, companies, and regulators in their assessment and communication on what is known about the hazards of different MNPs and their additives, using data available in the literature and generated by PlasticHeal. The outcome of PlasticRiskCat is a radar plot showing the level of evidence for a particular adverse outcome for an MNP or any plastic chemical. Each line on the radar plot represents a type of MNP or additive depending on the preferences of the users of PlasticRiskCat, and the axes of the radar plot illustrate the strength of evidence ranging from very strong to very weak.

The IMPTOX Health Outcome Assessment Framework is designed to systematically identify, analyse, and prioritise findings relevant to evaluating health outcomes — particularly allergies and asthma — associated with specific exposures or interventions. A key Health Outcome Assessment Framework integrates RA data to scientifically identify and quantify hazards that contribute to allergy-related health outcomes. The framework also delivers actionable insights, particularly by assessing the association between MNP exposure and allergies in a study population, with findings used to model impacts in other populations. These findings can

guide public health interventions, regulatory adjustments, and preventive strategies aimed at reducing allergy-related risks linked to MNP exposure through air and food pathways. The implementation of the IMPTOX framework provides a comprehensive understanding of how MNPs may increase an individual's risk of developing or exacerbating allergic responses to known allergens. It also highlights critical knowledge gaps for further refining RA and more effectively informing regulatory frameworks to mitigate these.

POLYRISK has developed an RAF for MNPs' impacts on human health with a special focus on inhalation. [20] The aim was to establish an approach that is based on the most recent state-of-the-art and well-established concepts, and capable of tackling the complexity of MNPs. POLYRISK's RAF combines different Integrative Approach to Testing and Assessment (IATA) and uses categorisation/grouping approaches to manage the broad range of physicochemical characteristics of MNPs. It starts with a basic physicochemical characterisation to assess whether the material of interest can be categorised as an MNP in general, followed by an assessment to determine the potential for inhalation exposure. Depending on the morphology (fibre- or particle-like), the RAF proposes IATAs for an appropriate toxicological assessment.

Knowledge Gaps and Challenges

1. Hazard Identification and Characterisation

- concentration-effect relationships on a wide range of different MNPs, in particular environmentally-aged or weathered MNPs that are relevant for real-life exposure,
- acute and long-term human health effects of MNPs, linked to relevant concentrations and exposure conditions,
- the combined effects of MNPs (i.e., physical effects) and plastic-associated chemicals (i.e., chemical effects),
- understanding of MNPs as carriers of other hazardous contaminants, including human pathogens,

- translational biomarkers based on the specific IATAs linked to specific AOP and NAMs, including *in silico* methods, tiered *in vitro* approaches using simple (cell lines) and advanced (stem cell-based organoids, co-cultures with relevant cells) culture methods.

2. Levels and Characteristics of Human Exposures

- lack of reliable and harmonised data on the environmental occurrence of MNPs (air, water, food, consumer products), including aged or weathered MNPs,
- lack of reliable and harmonised data on exposure of humans needed for assessment of long-term risks for human health, i.e., data of (aged/weathered) MNPs in real-world samples (air, water, food, biological matrices, etc.),
- lack of reliable and harmonised data on distribution of MNPs in target human organs, fluids, and tissues (e.g., blood, placenta, brain, etc.).

3. Vulnerable and At-Risk Populations

- lack of data (hazard and exposure data) on vulnerable groups of people or life stages that are most sensitive towards MNP exposure and/or effects, for example:
 - the unborn, infants and young children who, due to rapid development, are at greater risk from environmental toxins,
 - individuals with compromised health, such as those with weakened immune systems or co-existing medical conditions,
 - low-income communities may have increased pollution exposure,
 - workers in industries such as construction or waste management, material production, plastic recycling, textile production, automotive industry, agriculture, and food industry,
 - communities with higher exposure to environmental pollution, such as coastal populations affected by marine contamination.
- human biomonitoring data measured in relevant contexts or populations to define health-based guidance values.

Figure 5. Steps included in health risk assessments.

Research Needs

Immediate Needs (0–2 years / 2026–2028)

DEVELOP AGGREGATED EXPOSURE ASSESSMENT

Generation of – or ensuring access to – commercially relevant information about production, import volumes, use concentrations of different types of products, plastics and their additives, the use of this information to map exposure routes for different populations over time, and complete aggregated exposure assessment; data from realistic exposure scenarios that mimic environmental conditions.

PERFORM QUALITATIVE RISK ASSESSMENTS OF MNPs AND MIXTURES

Given the current limitations in quantitative data on MNPs, particularly for complex environmental mixtures, qualitative risk assessment approaches are essential. These methods can integrate existing knowledge on particle characteristics, hazard indicators, exposure scenarios, and mechanistic evidence to provide a structured evaluation of potential health risks in the absence of complete dose-response data. Developing transparent, tiered qualitative frameworks will allow preliminary risk classification of various MNP types and mixtures, support regulatory decision-making, and help prioritise substances for further testing and data generation.

Mid-Term Needs (2–5 years / 2027–2032)

UNDERSTAND EXPOSURE AND EFFECTS IN HUMAN POPULATIONS

Reliable biomonitoring techniques for MNPs need to be developed and employed in human populations to establish exposure levels in the EU population.

GENERATE HAZARD DATA FOR KEY PLASTIC TYPES

Generation of physicochemical and hazard data and information is needed on all key plastic types on the European market using existing and novel test systems including evaluation of the applicability of existing test systems and validation of novel test systems for regulatory purposes.

GENERATE HAZARD DATA FOR KEY PLASTIC MIXTURES

Generation of physicochemical and hazard data and information on all key plastic types in combination with their most used additives including evaluation of the applicability of existing test systems and SOP and validation of novel test systems for regulatory purposes.

UNDERSTAND HUMAN HEALTH RISKS THROUGH EPIDEMIOLOGICAL RESEARCH

Human health studies with reliable exposure assessment on

intermediate biological effects, early symptoms of disease stages, and health should be carried out in diverse settings.

Long-Term Needs (>5 years / beyond 2032)

DEVELOP QUANTITATIVE RISK ASSESSMENTS OF MNPs AND MIXTURES

Develop derived no-effect levels/derived minimal effect levels (DNELs/DMELs) for MNPs and MNP-mixtures when no-effect levels can be established for certain effects for each human subpopulation known to be or likely to be exposed.

ADDRESS SOCIAL DETERMINANTS AND HEALTH INEQUITIES IN MNP EXPOSURE AND RISK

Plastic-related health harms, including those linked to MNPs, are increasingly recognised to disproportionately affect marginalised communities and populations in low- and middle-income countries. To better understand and mitigate these inequities, it is essential to investigate how social determinants – such as geography, race/ethnicity, socioeconomic status, occupation, and lifestyle – shape exposure pathways and influence susceptibility to MNP-related health effects. This knowledge will support the development of targeted interventions, public health strategies, and policy actions aimed at reducing exposure among vulnerable populations and addressing underlying health disparities.

ASSESS AND AMEND EXISTING TEST GUIDELINES AND FRAMEWORKS

Guidelines for risk assessment, such as from OECD, ECHA, EFSA, and frameworks, such as Risk Characterisation Ratio (RCR), acceptable daily intake, derivation of Derived No Effect Level/Predicted Environmental Concentration (DNEL/PEC), margin of safety, grouping and read-across, and AOP/IATA need to be applied, evaluated and adjusted for specific properties of MNPs. SOPs need to be evaluated, and further developed for MNP testing needs, and novel test systems and frameworks need to be evaluated to ensure they are appropriate for regulatory purposes.

Mitigation Measures

An important normative value of the European Union is the precautionary principle, which states that lack of scientific certainty should not stand in the way of preventing potential harm to human health. Given current evidence for the harms inflicted by plastics on human health across all life stages, it is important to prevent further adverse impacts on human health by implementing evidence-based mitigation strategies, even in the absence of abundant evidence of the harms of MNPs. This transversal theme of mitigation has emerged during the consultations for this research roadmap as a central aspect.

Here we outline future research needs for developing mitigation strategies, based on CUSP findings and within the context of ongoing activities in the EU.

Research Needs

Immediate Needs (0–2 years / 2026–2028)

IDENTIFY ONGOING POLICY ACTIVITIES THAT CAN ADDRESS MNP EXPOSURE MITIGATION

Under the EU's Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, several concepts and tools are outlined and have been introduced/are being developed that can help reduce exposure to MNPs, such as the concept of essential use and the concept of safe and sustainable by design. There is a need to compile an overview of policy initiatives and legal frameworks which could be leveraged for reducing exposure to MNPs, such as the food contact materials regulation and the Chemicals Regulation REACH, which are both currently being revised. Based on these findings, input needs for evidence-based policy making can be identified.

IDENTIFY WHICH USES OF PLASTICS ARE ESSENTIAL

Define essential vs non-essential uses of plastics, so steps towards elimination of unnecessary plastic use can be taken. This can be based on the essential use concept developed for the Montreal Protocol and further refined for the per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). This work will require inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration.

PROMOTE PUBLIC AWARENESS AND BEHAVIOUR CHANGE TO REDUCE MNP EXPOSURE

Reducing human exposure to MNPs will require not only technical innovations and regulatory action but also effective public engagement. Research is needed to support the

development, testing, and implementation of interventions that promote awareness and encourage behaviour change in households, workplaces, and public settings. These interventions should be grounded in empirical evidence from the social and behavioural sciences on what motivates individuals and communities to adopt safer practices — such as reducing plastic use, avoiding products prone to shedding MNPs, and improving indoor environments. Communication strategies must be adapted to different population groups, considering literacy, language, and cultural context. This approach will empower individuals and amplify the impact of policy and technological solutions.

Mid-Term Needs (2–5 years / 2027–2032)

IDENTIFY CRITERIA FOR DEVELOPING LOW-MIGRATING PLASTIC MATERIALS THAT ARE SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE BY DESIGN

For plastic uses that are found to be essential, it is important to reduce migration of MNPs as much as possible. To achieve higher inertness of plastics, the principles for MNP migration need to be characterised.

DEVELOP AN ALTERNATIVE MATERIALS SUBSTITUTION FRAMEWORK

For applications where plastics are deemed non-essential, it is important to have a substitution framework in place that avoids regrettable substitution, such as the replacement of plastics with materials that have been less well-characterised in terms of their toxicity and human or environmental health impacts.

ASSESS MITIGATION STRATEGIES AND THE RISKS OF SUBSTITUTES

To ensure that efforts to reduce MNP exposure are effective and do not generate unintended consequences, it is essential to systematically evaluate mitigation strategies, including behavioural interventions, regulatory actions, and material innovation. Particular attention must be given to the potential health and environmental risks posed by substitutes such as bio-based or biodegradable plastics, which may degrade into MNPs with unknown toxicity profiles. Research should also assess the impact and effectiveness of upstream policy measures (e.g., product reformulation, plastic bans) and downstream consumer-focused actions (e.g., awareness campaigns, safe product choices). This work will support the development of evidence-based public health guidance and policy tools, and ensure that mitigation strategies — including material substitutions — are aligned with innovation policy, sustainability targets, and health equity goals, while avoiding unintended consequences.

APPLY LIFE CYCLE APPROACHES TO IDENTIFY UPSTREAM MNP SOURCES

In mitigation and risk governance strategies, adopt a whole-life-cycle perspective to identify key emission points across plastic production, usage, and waste phases. Life cycle assessments (LCA) can support targeted upstream interventions and more realistic modelling of environmental release scenarios.

Long-Term Needs (>5 years / beyond 2032)

EVALUATE ECONOMIC IMPACTS AND COST-EFFECTIVENESS OF POLICY MEASURES

Quantify the economic burden associated with MNP-related health and environmental impacts. Evaluate the cost-effectiveness of interventions (e.g., bans, taxes, labelling) and explore fiscal tools such as extended producer responsibility and eco-taxation to incentivize reduction and innovation.

WAY FORWARD

As outlined in this roadmap, there are many challenges, knowledge gaps and research needs that need to be addressed for reliable human health risk assessment of MNPs. The issue of plastics in general is highly complex and a wicked problem, with scientific, political, and societal complexity and uncertainty as well as a diversity in the views of the different stakeholders.

The research outlined in this roadmap can support addressing the challenge at hand by generating knowledge on MNPs to inform evidence-based policy making. Implementation of this roadmap will be successful if it is based on inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration, involves stakeholders, includes both natural and social scientists, enables the verification of novel methods for real-world settings (such as measurements of MNPs by enforcement labs), and enables awareness and capacity building for policy makers.

While continued research is essential to fully assess the risks of MNPs to human health, certain precautionary measures can be implemented immediately. Limiting unnecessary MNP exposure, particularly in products where safer alternatives exist, and establishing guidelines for food and water can help reduce potential risks, especially for vulnerable populations. Raising public awareness, encouraging industries to adopt best practices to minimise MNP release throughout a product's life cycle, and enhancing monitoring systems to track MNP levels in air, water, and food are also crucial steps. A precautionary yet proactive approach will help safeguard public health while ongoing research advances the scientific basis for comprehensive regulatory action (see Table 1).

As mitigation strategies are explored – including material substitution, product reformulation, and regulatory bans – it is essential to evaluate the potential for unintended consequences. Emerging alternatives such as biodegradable or bio-based plastics may still degrade into MNPs or introduce new toxicological concerns. Therefore, health risks of these substitutes must be systematically assessed in tandem with their environmental performance. Aligning such efforts with innovation policy and circular economy goals will help ensure that today's solutions do not become tomorrow's problems. This integrated approach to mitigation – considering health, sustainability, and system-level impacts – is crucial for effective and future-proof policymaking.

Plastics are central to society, but they also have many adverse health impacts associated with their production, use, and end of life. In contrast to the harms of MNPs which are still being investigated and quantified, other adverse impacts of plastics are well known, for example their property of non-inertness leading to the leaching or gassing out of chemical constituents. Nevertheless, it will be challenging to transition away from plastics as the material of choice for many applications. Reliable evidence is therefore needed to enable this transition without creating rebound effects.

Box III. References

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All CUSP publications can be found on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/cusp-research/re-cords?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Box IV. Glossary

AOP

Adverse Outcome Pathway

CMR

Carcinogenicity, Mutagenicity, and Reproductive

DG

Distorted Grid

DLS

Dynamic Light Scattering

DMEL(s)

Derived Minimal Effect Level(s)

DNEL/PEC

Derived No-Effect Level/Predicted Environmental Concentration

DNEL(s)

Derived No-Effect Level(s)

FAIR

Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

FTIR

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

IATA

Integrated Approach to Testing and Assessment

ILC

Inter-Laboratory Comparison

LD

Laser Diffraction

LCA

Life Cycle Assessments

LDIR

Laser Direct Infrared Imaging Spectroscopy

MNP

Micro- and Nanoplastic

μ-FTIR

Micro-Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

μ-RAMAN

Micro-Raman Spectroscopy

NAM

New Approach Methodology

PA

Polyamide

PBK

Physiologically Based Kinetic

PE

Polyethylene

PET

Polyethylene Terephthalate

PFAS

Polyfluoroalkyl Substances

PLA

Poly lactide

PMDCS

PlasticsFatE's "prospective multi-criteria decision system"

PP

Polypropylene

PS

Polystyrene

PVC

Polyvinyl Chloride

Py-GC/MS

Pyrolysis-Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry

RA

Risk Assessment

RAF(s)

Risk Assessment Framework(s)

RCR

Risk Characterisation Ratio

QA/QC

Quality Assurance/Quality Control

RCR

Risk Characterisation Ratio

SOP

Standard Operating Procedure

TED-GC/MS

Thermal Extraction and Desorption-Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectrometry

TWRP

Tyre Wear Rubber Particles

UNEP

United Nations Environment Programme

WoE

Weight of Evidence